

1 **Microbial Soil Respiration and its dependency on Carbon Inputs, Soil Temperature**
2 **and Moisture**

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1 **Abstract**

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3 This experiment was designed to study three determinant factors in decomposition
4 patterns of soil organic matter (SOM): temperature, water and carbon (C) inputs. The
5 study combined field measurements with soil lab incubations and ends with a modeling
6 framework based on the results obtained. Soil respiration was periodically measured at an
7 oak savanna woodland and a ponderosa pine plantation. Intact soils cores were collected
8 at both ecosystems, including soils with most labile carbon burnt off, soils with some
9 labile carbon gone, and soils with fresh inputs of labile carbon. Two treatments, dry-field
10 condition and field capacity were applied to an incubation that lasted 111 days. Short-
11 term temperature changes were applied to the soils periodically to quantify temperature
12 responses. This was done to prevent confounding results associated with different pools
13 of carbon that would result by exposing treatments chronically to different temperature
14 regimes. This paper discusses the role of the above defined environmental factors on the
15 variability of soil C dynamics. At the seasonal scale, temperature and water were,
16 respectively, the main limiting factors controlling soil CO₂ efflux for the ponderosa pine
17 and the oak savanna ecosystems. Spatial and seasonal variations in plant activity (root
18 respiration and exudates production) exerted a strong influence over the seasonal and
19 spatial variation of soil metabolic activity. Mean residence times of bulk SOM were
20 significantly lower at the Nitrogen (N)-rich deciduous savanna than at the N- limited
21 evergreen dominated pine ecosystem. At shorter time scales (daily) SOM decomposition
22 was controlled primarily by temperature during wet periods and by the combined effect
23 of water and temperature during dry periods. Secondary control was provided by the
24 presence/absence of plant derived C inputs (exudation). Further analyses of SOM
25 decomposition suggest that factors such as changes in the decomposer community, stress-
26 induced changes in the metabolic activity of decomposers or SOM stabilization patterns
27 remain unresolved, but should also be considered in future SOM decomposition studies.
28 Observations and confounding factors associated to SOM decomposition patterns and its
29 temperature sensitivity are summarized in the modeling framework.

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1 Introduction

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3 The soil is the largest terrestrial carbon pool (Post et al. 1982). Stored soil carbon results
4 from an imbalance between organic matter produced by plants and its decomposition
5 back into the atmosphere as CO₂. The large pool of carbon in the soil is vulnerable to
6 climatic warming and its potential loss may amplify further warming (Cox et al. 2000).
7 However, current predictions are based on empirical models because there is a general
8 lack of knowledge about the mechanisms that influence decomposition of soil organic
9 matter, SOM.

10
11 Among the factors affecting SOM decomposition, temperature, soil moisture and plant C
12 inputs are perhaps the most relevant. Regarding the temperature sensitivity of
13 decomposition, kinetic theory predicts that temperature sensitivity of SOM
14 decomposition should increase as the degree of substrate complexity increases (Bosatta
15 and Agren 1998). Because the bulk of SOM is formed of old, long-chained organic
16 molecules, an increase of temperature will therefore affect the storage of these old
17 organic fractions more. However, other studies have shown very contradictory results
18 regarding temperature sensitivity of different organic matter fractions (Kirschbaum 1995,
19 Katterer et al 1998, Trumbore et al. 1996, Liski et al. 1999, Giardina and Ryan 2003,
20 Fang et al. 2005, Fierer et al 2003, Fierer et al 2005).

21
22 Soil water content is another important variable for predicting organic matter
23 decomposition and soil CO₂ efflux (Xu and Qi 2001a, Reichstein et al. 2002, Xu et al.
24 2004, Tang and Baldocchi 2005). Drought limits the physiological performance of
25 microbes and the diffusion of nutrients in the soil pore space (Harris 1981, Papendick &
26 Campbell 1981, Robertson et al. 1993). In general, soil metabolic activity decreases as
27 soils dry out below a certain limit (Howard and Howard 1993, Davidson et al. 1998, Xu
28 and Qi 2001, Reichstein et al. 2002, Curiel Yuste et al. 2003). Most studies have focused
29 on either temperature or water effects on SOM decomposition but only a few have
30 explored the combined effect of both (Howard and Howard 1993). Given the projected
31 decreases in precipitation and increases in temperatures projected for Mediterranean
32 systems (Gibelin and Deque 2003, Kueppers et al. 2005), it is particularly important to
33 understand how the interaction of both factors may affect SOM decomposition.

34
35 At the scale of a plant canopy, soil respiration may become decoupled from temperature
36 and, instead, be coupled to antecedent or current rates of photosynthesis. This is because
37 photosynthate translocated to roots stimulates their autotrophic respiration and because
38 root exudates feed microbes, which stimulates microbial respiration (Kuzyakov and
39 Cheng 2001, 2004, Hogberg et al. 2001, Bowling et al., 2002; Gleixner et al., 2005;
40 Grayston et al., 1997; Tang et al., 2005a; Baldocchi et al., 2006). The degree of coupling
41 depends on the time scale at which soil respiration is correlated with photosynthesis. On
42 seasonal/annual time scales, soil respiration correlates directly with gross primary
43 productivity (*GPP*) (Janssens et al. 2001; Raich and Tufekciogul 2000). Conversely, soil
44 respiration on hourly to weekly time scales is sensitive to antecedent rates of
45 photosynthesis (Hogberg et al 2001, Bowling et al. 2002, McDowell et al 2004, Tang et
46 al. 2005a, Baldocchi et al 2006).

1
2 We designed an experiment to explore how these factors affect SOM decomposition at
3 different time and spatial scales. The experimental design includes field respiration
4 measurements and ‘lab-based’ studies of SOM. The ultimate aim of the manuscript is to
5 create a conceptual framework to: 1. Encourage new experimental directions in the quest
6 for understanding the mechanisms involved in decomposition of SOM; and 2. Inspire the
7 development of new, mechanistic-based modeling exercises.

8 9 **Materials and methods**

10 11 *Sites Description*

12
13 Field measurements and soil sampling occurred at two ecosystems in northern California,
14 a ponderosa pine plantation and an oak savanna. The pine plantation is located adjacent
15 to the University of California Blodgett Forest Research Station at 38°53’42.9’’N,
16 120°37’57.9’’W at an altitude of 1315 m. The vegetation is dominated by ponderosa pine
17 (*Pinus ponderosa* L.) with occasional other tree species. The major understory shrubs are
18 *Arctostaphylos manzanita* (Manzanita) and *Ceanothus cordulatus* (Ceanothus). In spring
19 2003 tree density was ~510 trees per hectare; total one sided leaf area index (L_{AI}) was
20 2.49, mean tree diameter at breast height was 12.0 cm, mean tree height was 4.7 m (mean
21 shrubs height ~ 1.0 m), and basal area was 9.6 m² ha⁻¹. The site is characterized by a
22 Mediterranean climate, with warm dry summers and cold wet winters. Annual
23 precipitation averages 1290 mm, with the majority of precipitation falling between
24 September and May. Daily temperature averages range from 14–27 °C during summer
25 and from 0–9 °C during winter. The soil is relatively uniform and comprised of 60% sand
26 and 29%. The site is managed for commercial purposes. More information about
27 management practices can be found in Misson et al. (2005).

28
29 The oak savanna field site (Tonzi Ranch) is located at 38.4311° N, 120.966° W. The
30 altitude of the site is 177 m and the terrain is relatively flat. The woodland overstorey
31 consists of scattered blue oak trees (*Quercus douglasii*) with occasional grey pine trees
32 (*Pinus sabiniana*). The understorey consists of exotic annual grasses and herbs; the
33 species include *Brachypodium distachyon*, *Hypochaeris glabra*, *Bromus madritensis*, and
34 *Cynosurus echinatus*. The trees covered 40% of the landscape, with a mean height of
35 10.1 m +/- 4.7 m, mean trunk height of 1.5m +/- 1.6 m , mean crown radius of 2.8m +/-
36 1.6 m and leaf area index equals 0.65 (Baldocchi et al. 2004). The overstorey and
37 understorey vegetation operate in and out of phase with each other over the course of a
38 year. Soil is classified as loamy, mixed, superactive, thermic Lithic Haploxerepts
39 (USDA). Depth of bedrock ranges from 25 to 70 cm but hardly exceed the 50 cm, which
40 makes this soil relatively shallow. The climate of the region is Mediterranean. The mean
41 annual temperature is 16.3°C, and 559 mm of precipitation fall per year, as determined
42 from over 30 years of data from a nearby weather station at Ione, California.

43
44 The ecological and meteorological features of the two ecosystems under study have been
45 characterized in other papers (Misson et al. 2005, Baldocchi et al. 2004).

1 *Field measurements*

2
3 During spring and summer 2005 soil respiration was measured twice a month at both
4 ecosystems. We used a LI6400-09 soil chamber connected to an LI-6400 portable
5 photosynthesis system (LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE). We used collars with a height of 4.4
6 cm and a diameter of 11 cm that were inserted into the soil for measuring soil respiration.
7 In the oak savanna site, 30 collars were used to cover the spatial variability of soil
8 respiration in this ecosystem (Tang and Baldocchi 2005). We defined understory soil
9 respiration as that recorded in the vicinity of the trees, 3 or less meters away from the
10 trunk while open soil respiration as that recorded far from the tree influence (Tang and
11 Baldocchi 2005) that we defined as at least 20 meters away from trees. In the ponderosa
12 pine ecosystems, two 20 × 20 m² sampling plots were established, 40 m apart within the
13 footprint area of the meteorological tower and a 3 X 3 m² trenched plot. Typically, soil
14 respiration was measured about 3–4 rounds in a day. Soil temperature at 5 cm in soil
15 profile was collected with a soil thermistor next to each collar. Volumetric soil moisture
16 content was measured continuously in the field at several depths in the soil with
17 frequency domain reflectometry sensors (Theta Probe model ML2-X, Delta-T Devices,
18 Cambridge, UK). Sensors were placed at various depths in the soil (5, 10, 20 and 50 cm)
19 and were calibrated using the gravimetric method. In the oak savannah, profiles of soil
20 moisture (0–15, 15–30, 30–45 and 45–60 cm) were made periodically and manually
21 using an enhanced time domain reflectometer (Moisture Point, model 917, E.S.I.
22 Environmental Sensors Inc., Victoria, Canada). In Blodgett we also installed two
23 moisture sensors at 10 cm, one in the control plot and one in the trenched plot (TDR,
24 CS615 Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT) for continuously measuring soil moisture at
25 5 min intervals. Dataloggers (CR10X and 23X, Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT)
26 were programmed to store temperature and moisture data every 5 min. Due to technical
27 problems, only scarce data was available from this TDR's during 2005.

28
29 For more methodological information about soil respiration measurements see Tang and
30 Baldocchi (2005) and Tang et al. (2005b). Soil water content was recorded continuously
31 in the vicinity of the meteorological tower at each site.

32
33 *Laboratory Incubations design*

34
35 Intact soil cores were collected during the 29 and 30 July 2005. By this date rains at the
36 site had stopped by 42 days, the grass was dead and the trees were still
37 photosynthesizing. In the ponderosa pine site photosynthetic activity of vegetation was at
38 its peak (personal communication). Undisturbed soil cores of 80 cm³ (4.4 x 4.4 x 5 cm)
39 were collected from the upper part of the soil profile (0-5 cm) using a stainless steel core
40 soil sampler. Soil cores were kept in their stainless steel container. By keeping intact
41 cores with their original bulk density, we were able to assess changes in volumetric water
42 content via gravimetric methods and apply water retention curves to assess changes in
43 soil water potential (see below). For this study, four different soils were chosen: in the
44 oak savanna site soils were taken from open areas (oak savanna open) where only grass
45 grows and contribution of trees is minimal (Baldocchi et al. 2004) and under the tree
46 canopy (oak savanna understory) where there is significant contribution from trees and

1 grasses. In the ponderosa pine plantation, samples were taken from the two adjacent
2 control plots (Misson et al 2006) that we refer to as ‘ponderosa pine control’ and from the
3 trenched plot (3 x 3 m) established in 2000, that we refer to as ‘ponderosa pine trenched’.
4 Because the trenched plot was established 5 years before the samples were taken for this
5 study, we assume the mean age of the organic matter in the trenched plot to be older than
6 in the control plot. The experimental design therefore includes treatments with most
7 labile carbon burnt off (trenched plot), treatments with some labile carbon gone (dead
8 grass of open areas in oak savanna), and treatments with fresh inputs of labile carbon
9 (oak and pine understories areas).

10
11 To infer the minimum number of samples required we used the standard deviation
12 obtained from soil respiration measurements made during period of maximal spatial
13 variability and the equation:

$$14 \quad n = [z_{\alpha/2} * \sigma / E] \quad \text{equation 1}$$

15
16
17 Where n is the sample size, $z_{\alpha/2}$ is known as the critical value and σ is the population
18 standard deviation. To cover the spatial variability of soil respiration with a confidence
19 interval of 95% and an error of no more than 25%, 3 collars were needed for the trenched
20 plot and 6 for the other three soils. 3 (trenched plot) and 6 (three other soils) soil samples
21 per soil (x4) and per treatment (x2) were therefore collected.

22
23 Soils were sampled in a treatment from an area with a radius of 1 m and sampling plots
24 were separated by at least 30 meters from each other. Sampling circles were defined
25 randomly within the footprint of the micrometeorological tower. Within each of these
26 locations, two sub-locations were defined also randomly and 3 samples were collected
27 close to each other. From the three samples collected at each sub-location, one was used
28 for analyses (soil water content, soil water potential, total carbon and nitrogen), one was
29 kept at field soil moisture (called dry) and incubated at 20 °C five hours after being
30 collected and the last one was placed over water-saturated sponges during 24 hours,
31 moistening the soil by capillarity until the soil matrix reached maximum water holding
32 capacity values (called wet). After 24 hours, the samples were placed in the incubator at
33 20 °C. Soil water content at the samples was maintained by adding water periodically
34 (approximately once a week) to the samples based on weight loss. In the trenched plot,
35 the sampling strategy consisted of choosing randomly three sub-locations within the 3 x 3
36 plot. As in the other three soil types, three samples were collected at each sub-location (1
37 for analyses, one incubated dry and one incubated wet). Therefore 3 samples were
38 incubated for each treatment (dry and wet) and 3 samples were used for laboratory
39 analyses (Table 1).

40
41 To assess the temperature sensitivity of soil decomposition at different stages of the
42 incubation, 7 temperature cycles were performed. These occurred at days 2, 7, 16, 24,
43 51, 81 and 111 after incubation started. During a cycle, temperatures was increased from
44 20 to 35 °C and then decreased again to the basal temperature (20 °C) with 5 °C steps
45 every four hours. In total, each temperature cycle took 32 hours. Samples were
46 maintained at 20 °C between temperature cycles. Three thermocouples were inserted at

1 three different depths within the soil cores (0.5 cm from surface, 2.5 cm depth and 4.5 cm
2 depth) to study possible gradients in temperature within the collars during these
3 temperature cycles. As may be expected from a volume of soil with heat capacity and
4 edges, temperatures in the upper part of the sample equilibrated faster with the incubator
5 temperature (data not shown), but the inner part of the sample needed at least three hours
6 to equilibrate with the incubator temperature. To avoid these temperature gradients, soil
7 CO₂ evolution was measured one hour after soil temperature was equilibrated within the
8 sample.

9 10 *Soil analyses*

11
12 Several soil characteristics were measured using the soil samples spared from analyses.
13 Bulk density, soil moisture, soil C and N concentrations and grams of litter and fine roots
14 present in the samples were estimated. We defined litter as organic matter present in the
15 soil samples still not completely degraded and that could be visually distinguishable from
16 the bulk of the organic matter and the soil (e. g. needles, burk, etc..). Fine roots were not
17 separated either into live and dead, nor were they divided into diameter classes. In the
18 oak savanna open, all fine roots were from grasses and were dead at the time of sampling.
19 Soil moisture was estimated gravimetrically, by drying the samples during 48 hours at 75
20 °C. By estimating the dry weight of the samples contained within the known volume of
21 the collar (80 cm³) we estimated the bulk density of the sample. Results are presented in
22 Table 1.

23 24 *Soil respiration system*

25
26 To measure soil CO₂ efflux we built a dynamic flow-through system which was operated
27 under closed and non-steady state conditions. Concentrations of CO₂ in the system were
28 measured with a Li-Cor 6262 infrared gas analyzer (Li-Cor, Lincoln, NE). Two-valved
29 acrylic flow meters (10 LPM precision) maintained an air flow of around 1 LPM through
30 the closed system including Teflon tubing (FEP ¼"OD 3/16" ID) and the soil chamber.
31 At this air flow pressure fluctuations within the system were minimal, which
32 consequently minimized pressure-related variations in the CO₂ readings. A Campbell
33 Scientific data logger (Model CR10X) recorded CO₂, water vapor, air temperature and
34 pressure in the soil chamber every second. The parallel recording of temperature and
35 pressure in the chamber allowed us to correct CO₂ concentrations for fluctuations in both
36 parameters in real time using the ideal gas equation. To avoid pulses of CO₂ due to
37 pressure fluctuations created by opening and closing the lid, we reduced the measurement
38 interval to that interval with minimal pressure fluctuations (Figure 1). The short time used
39 to measure the increase in CO₂ within the jar head space (40-60 seconds) reduced
40 diffusion artifacts that may affect the flux estimates (Pumpanen et al. 2004). Moreover,
41 the sampling frequency of the system (1 Hertz) improves the statistical fit obtained over
42 standard methodologies that produce a limited number of readings, such as closed static
43 chambers that sample the air episodically with syringes (Livingston & Hutchinson 1995).

44 45 *Calculation of decomposition rates and soil organic matter mean residence time*

1 Soil respiration was calculated from the initial slope in CO₂ concentration increase as a
2 function of time (normally 40 second time interval) within the closed loop (Livingston
3 GP, Hutchinson GL 1995)

$$4 \quad F_c = (dCO_2/dt - a) * t/V_s \quad \text{equation 2}$$

6 where F_c is the total soil CO₂ evolved from the soil sample during the sampling interval
7 (μmol), dCO_2/dt is the change in CO₂ concentration (ppm) within the system during the
8 sampling interval, t is the sample interval (s), a is the intercept of the linear function and
9 V_s is the volume of the system (l). Volume of the system was calculated by injecting
10 within the system a known quantity of CO₂ and applying the following dilution function:
11

$$12 \quad V_s = R * T/P * \Delta CO_2 / \text{ppm}_f \quad \text{equation 3}$$

14 Where V_s is the unknown volume of the system (l), R the Universal Gas Constant ($8.31 * 10^{-3}$
15 $\text{L kPa mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), T and P are respectively the observed temperature (K) and air
16 pressure (kPa) at measurement time, ΔCO_2 is known injected quantity of CO₂ (60 ml of
17 air with 600 ppm concentration of CO₂ = $0.94 \mu\text{mol CO}_2$) and ppm_f the final CO₂
18 concentration within the closed system. Prior to CO₂ addition, the system was flushed
19 with N to achieve zero CO₂ concentration. A second syringe was installed as buffering
20 volume avoiding overpressure within the system when injecting the 60 ml air. Volume of
21 the system was also corrected by pore space of soil sample within the closed system
22 based on the bulk density of the sample and the density of mineral particles (2.65 g/cm^3),
23 assuming free pore space for dry samples and saturated pore space for wet samples.
24

25
26 Soil CO₂ flux (F_c) was then converted to $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (F_a) by the surface of the collar
27 ($12.6 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2$). Additionally, MRT of the bulk soil C (MRT_{soil} ; y^{-1}) was calculated
28 during the incubation with the remaining soil C (g) divided by the observed
29 decomposition rates (g C s^{-1}) at each measurement time. Remaining carbon in soil was
30 calculated by integrating the total soil CO₂ evolved (TCR) during sampling days using a
31 simple linear function.
32

$$33 \quad TCR = \sum (c * t + b) dt \quad \text{equation 4}$$

34
35 Where TCR is the total amount of C (gC) respired during a given time interval, t is time
36 in days within the given time interval and c and b are parameters. Total soil C remaining
37 was then calculated by subtracting the cumulative amount of C respired from the initial
38 amount of C.
39

40 According to the manufacturer (Li-Cor, Lincoln, NE) the IRGA can detect changes of 0.2
41 ppm at 10 Hz (sensitivity). Translated to fluxes units and the sampling frequency of the
42 system (1Hertz) means that at standard conditions (40 seconds range, at ambient CO₂
43 concentrations, 25 °C and 101 kPa air pressure) the detection limit of our system was of
44 $0.06 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, typically one order of magnitude smaller than the fluxes detected in
45 dry soils (see below).
46

1 The contribution of any live root respiration to total efflux was assumed to be marginal.
2 First, it is likely that living fine roots in the soil cores died soon after excision because
3 fine roots exhaust their carbohydrate storage quickly due to their high rates of respiration
4 (Pregitzer 1998). Second, fine roots of grasses were dead by the time of sampling, which
5 makes only the scarcer tree fine roots the active ones. And thirdly, to minimize
6 confounding effects of respiration by any residual live fine root on soil CO₂ efflux, we
7 initiated our first set of respiration measurements 48 hours after field sampling.

8 9 *Sensitivity to temperature and soil moisture of soil CO₂ efflux*

10
11 To assess the relative increase in soil decomposition with temperature, we used the Q₁₀
12 function. Q₁₀ computes the relative increase in decomposition rate per 10 °C difference.
13 To avoid errors associated with multiple parameter fitting (Hyvönen et al. 2005,
14 Reichstein et al 2005), we reduced the parameter fitting to Q₁₀, using the known values of
15 F_{m20} as basal respiration rates.

$$16 \quad F_a = F_{a20} * Q_{10}^{T-20/10} \quad \text{equation 5}$$

17
18
19 In Equation 5, F_a is the measured soil CO₂ efflux (F_c on *equation 2*) normalized for the
20 amount of remaining soil C, F_{a20} is the measured F_a at 20 °C, Q₁₀ is the relative change in
21 F_a with 10 °C increases and T is the temperature of soil at measurement time. We fitted
22 this exponential function at each temperature cycle, for each of the four studied soils for
23 each water treatment (wet and dry). The function was also fitted to the seasonal evolution
24 of soil respiration and soil temperature obtained from field measurements in the
25 ponderosa pine site during 2005 (no correlation was found with temperature for oak
26 savanna respiration).

27
28 Seasonal evolution of soil respiration, as a function of soil moisture, was fitted to a
29 sigmoidal Boltzman-type function:

$$30 \quad SR = b + (a-b)/(1 + \exp((SWC-c)/d)) \quad \text{equation 6}$$

31
32
33 Where SR is soil respiration (μmol m⁻² s⁻¹) recorded in the field, a, b, c and d are
34 parameters and SWC is the soil water content (% vol) at 15 cm into the soil. This
35 equation was applied to field soil respiration recorded in the oak savanna soils during
36 2005.

37 38 *Calculation of soil carbon pools*

39
40 There are several equations that have inferred the labile and recalcitrant C pools based on
41 the changes in the slope of the C mineralization along the incubation period (Sleutel et al.
42 2005, Katterer et al. 1998, Townsend et al. 1997). These equations assume that the C
43 mineralized initially has a fast turnover and is labile (fast pool), while the remaining
44 fraction has a slow turnover and is recalcitrant (slow pool) (Townsend et al. 1997). In this
45 study we used and compared results from three different two-pool carbon models:
46

1 $C_{cum}(t) = C_f * [1 - (e^{-k_f * t})] + (C_{total} - C_f) * [1 - (e^{-k_s * t})]$ *equation 7*

2 $C_{cum}(t) = C_f * [1 - (e^{-k_f * t})] + k_s * t$ *equation 8*

3 $C_{rate}(t) = k_f * (C_f * e^{-k_f * t}) + k_s * ((C_{total} - C_f) * e^{-k_s * t})$ *equation 9*

4

5 $C_{cum}(t)$ is the cumulative mineralized C at a certain time of the incubation, expressed as
 6 F_a ($gC\ d^{-1}\ m^{-2}$), k_f and k_s are the rate constants of the fast and slow C pool (d^{-1}), C_f is the
 7 carbon content of the fast pool and C_{total} the calculated soil C (Table 2) ($KgC\ m^{-2}$).
 8 *Equation 7* has been used in Breland (1994), Franzluebbers et al. (1994) and Bernal et al.
 9 (1998), *Equation 8* has been used in Alvarez and Alvarez (2000) and *Equation 9* is
 10 attributed to Robertson et al. (1999). The fit was improved by constraining the size of the
 11 slow pool (assumed C_s as $C_{total} - C_f$) (McLauchlan and Hobbie 2004). Mean residence time
 12 of the fast (MRT_f) and the slow (MRT_s) C pools were then calculated using the rate
 13 constant: $MRT_i = 1/k_i$; where $i = f$ (fast pool) or s (slow pool).

14

15 Contribution of the fast and the slow pool can then be estimated with a mass balance
 16 approach:

17

18 $MRT_o = MRT_f * \delta_f + MRT_s * \delta_s$ *equation 10*

19 $1 = \delta_f + \delta_s$ *equation 11*

20

21 Where MRT_o , MRT_f and MRT_s are the mean residence time for the bulk soil C at time 0,
 22 fast C pool and slow C pool respectively, and δ_f and δ_s are the relative contribution of the
 23 fast and the slow C pool to the total flux. Relative contribution of the fast and the slow
 24 pool (δ_f and δ_s) was calculated for the microbial decomposition at the time of collection.

25

26 MRT_o (mean residence time of soil organic matter at time 0) was calculated by fitting a
 27 second order polynomial function to the temporal evolution of the calculated MRT_{soil} :

28

29 $MRT_{soil} = MRT_o + (b * t) + (c * t^2)$ *equation 12*

30

31 Where MRT_{soil} is the calculated MRT (yr) of the bulk soil for a given moment of the
 32 incubation, MRT_o represents the MRT_{soil} of soils at time of sample recollection (time 0), t
 33 is time in days and b and c are parameters. This function was fitted to both the wet and
 34 dry lab treatments for the four soils (table 3).

35

36 *Statistics*

37

38 Analysis of variance and non-linear regressions were performed using the curve fitter
 39 routines in Origin 5.0.

40

41

1 **Results and Discussion**

3 *Soil respiration- and soil decomposition-derived CO₂ efflux*

5 In general, field- and lab-based estimates of soil CO₂ efflux were in good agreement
6 (Figures 2 and 3), despite the fact they have different components. However,
7 disagreements between field (Figure 2) and lab based (Figure 3) soil CO₂ efflux occurred
8 and are informative, too. For example, in the pine trenched plot, soil CO₂ emissions were
9 higher than lab-based soil CO₂ estimates (Figures 2a and 3a). In contrast, lab-based
10 estimates of soil CO₂ efflux in open oak savanna from dry soils (Figures 3c) were higher
11 than those obtained in the field (Figure 2d). Lower lab-based rates of SOM in the
12 trenched pine soils were expected since soil cores only covered the 5 first cm of soil,
13 whereas Blodgett soil stores more C below this depth (Goldstein 2000). Regarding the
14 disagreement of fluxes in the dry savanna soils, soil respiration measurements during the
15 driest periods were taken at higher soil temperatures (around 30-40 C, see Figure 2e) than
16 those of the incubation (20 C). The agreement between field- and lab-based soils CO₂
17 efflux was, therefore, better when they were normalized to similar temperature and soil
18 moisture levels (Figures 4c and 4d).

20 Two-pool models, fit to cumulative mineralized C data, are commonly used to quantify
21 SOM fractionation (McLauchlan and Hobbie 2004, Sleutel et al. 2005). Here we
22 compared three different models to assess the accuracy of these techniques. On the non-
23 trenched plots, the three models fitted the data collected in this study well and had
24 coefficients significantly different from zero on the 95% confidence interval (Table 2).
25 In addition coefficient values were within those published using similar models in other
26 studies (Alvarez and Alvarez 2000, Sleutel et al 2005, Dalias et al 2001).

28 Generally, longer (> 6 months) lab incubation periods are used to produce reliable
29 coefficients for two-pool models (Townsend et al., 1997). To assess if the duration of our
30 111 day incubation study introduced any bias or error on the determination of the two
31 pool model coefficients we performed the following calculation. We assumed that
32 decomposition rates at day 180 were 33% lower than those of 111 and recomputed the
33 model coefficients. This artificial extension of the incubation period was found to modify
34 the computation of rate coefficients by less than 10%.

36 *Comparison of soil C dynamics of two contrasting ecosystems*

38 Soil respiration peaked during early spring in the oak savanna soils and during summer in
39 ponderosa pine soils (Figures 2a and 2d). By sampling collection date (arrows in Figure
40 2), pine plantation experienced the highest soil temperatures and the lowest soil moisture
41 values of the year. Soil moisture levels in the pine site nonetheless sufficed to maintain
42 high soil metabolic rates, in contrast to the strong metabolic limitations observed at the
43 savanna site (Figure 2a and 2d). In the oak savanna soil, temperatures were near its peak
44 and soil moisture at its nadir by sampling collection date (below panels in Figure 2) and
45 soil respiration values were already close to the lowest of that year. Though field soil
46 respiration was more than four times higher in the ponderosa pine plantation than in the

1 oak savanna system, SOM decomposition rates were similar (solid points in Figure 3).
2 Therefore, most of the metabolic variability observed in the field was likely associated to
3 differences in autotrophic activity. In summer ponderosa pine ecosystem reaches its
4 maximal photosynthetic activity (Misson et al. 2006), while in oak savanna ecosystems
5 annual grasses are dead and oak trees activity is strongly limited by drought (Baldocchi et
6 al. 2004).

7
8 Environmental control over the variation of metabolic activity in the field appeared very
9 different at both sites (Figure 4). While seasonal variation of soil CO₂ efflux in the
10 ponderosa pine ecosystem was mainly limited by temperature (Figures 4a and 4b), soil
11 moisture was the factor limiting the seasonal variation in metabolic activity in the oak
12 savanna site (Figure 4c and 4d). The low temperatures in the ponderosa pine ecosystem
13 limited substantially the activity of organisms (plants and microbes) during winter and
14 only the seasonal increase in temperature allowed organisms to increase their soil
15 metabolic activity (panels above in Figure 2). Temperature remained relatively high in
16 the savanna site during winter and early spring which stimulates the activity of plants and
17 microbes (panels below Figure 2). The increase in temperature coincided with the
18 decrease in soil water availability during spring, triggering the senescence of the annual
19 grasses in the open areas (Baldocchi et al. 2004). Because grasslands occupy
20 approximately 60% of the savanna ecosystem, this decline resulted in an overall decrease
21 in soil metabolic activity of the savanna during spring and summer. Despite the proximity
22 of both Mediterranean ecosystems, intra-regional differences in climate and phenology of
23 vegetation, therefore, define the seasonal evolution of soil respiration.

24 *Role of plant activity on soil C dynamics*

25
26
27 The relative absence of fast pool carbon (C_f) in the trenched soils, in contrast to non-
28 trenched soils (Table 2), suggests a connection between plant activity and the existence of
29 labile carbon that is quickly decomposed in the fast pool. Within the oak savanna site, C_f
30 under the active trees doubled that under the dead grasses of the open areas (Table 2).
31 Despite the higher soil temperatures and moisture, both soil respiration (Figure 2d) and
32 microbial decomposition rates (Figure 3c and 3d) were higher under active trees than
33 under dead annual grasses. Active plants are continuously releasing organic material to
34 soil. Such exudates exist in the form of easily decomposable substrate such as of simple
35 sugars, amino acids and organic acids (Lynch and Whipps 1990, Grayston et al. 1996,
36 Gleixner et al. 2005, Norton and Firestone 1991). The importance of exudation does not
37 just lie in its easily decomposable nature, but in the stimulation of older more recalcitrant
38 SOM in what is called priming effect (Kuzyakov et al. 2000, Kuzyakov and Cheng 2001,
39 Kuzyakov and Bol 2006, Fontaine et al. 2003).

40
41 The important contribution of this fast C pool to the total decomposition-derived CO₂
42 efflux (Figure 5) and its short life span (Table 1) indicates its important role in the short-
43 term variation of soil respiration. Tang et al. (2005a) showed how photosynthesis
44 strongly controlled soil respiration in the studied oak savanna system, with a lag of 7-12
45 hours during the summer. Studies in spring wheat and maize plants indicate that
46 photosynthetic-induced priming effect via root exudation may account for a substantial

1 increase in SOM decomposition rates and its short-term temporal variation (Kuzyakov
2 and Cheng 2001, 2004). The observed differences between trenched and non-trenched
3 soils, and understorey and open savanna soils could, therefore, be partly attributed to
4 plant activity and the active synergy between living plants and soil microorganisms. This
5 photosynthetic effect, therefore, may account for part of the unaccounted variation
6 typically associated to current soil respiration models, parameterized with only
7 temperature and moisture.

8
9 The role of plant activity on soil CO₂ efflux was also observed at longer temporal scale
10 (Figure 4). In contrast to the similarity in Q₁₀ values between lab and seasonal data in
11 trenched pine soils (Figure 4a), values of seasonal Q₁₀ of the control plot were
12 substantially higher than the Q₁₀ of approximately 2 obtained from lab estimates (Figure
13 4b). These differences between control and root-free soils may reflect the confounding
14 effect of seasonality of fine root growth, activity and exudates deposition which in turn
15 depends upon photosynthetic supply from plants (Curiel Yuste et al. 2004, Davidson et
16 al. 2006, Sampson et al. in press). In oak savanna soils the effect of seasonality of C
17 inputs in soil respiration can be also noticed (Figure 4c and 4d). Lab decomposition rates
18 (calculated using the initial lab-obtained Q₁₀ and normalized for field temperatures and
19 soil moistures) were lower than field respiration rates for open area soils (Figure 4c). This
20 is probably because the period at which soil respiration values were recorded (spring;
21 closed symbols) grasses were active, but when soil cores were collected (summer, open
22 symbols) grasses were already dead. In contrast SOM decomposition rates were higher
23 than field soil respiration for understorey area soils (Figure 4d), probably because soil
24 respiration was recorded when the trees were dormant while soil cores were collected
25 when the trees were active.

26 27 *Mean residence time of soil organic matter*

28
29 Mean residence times from the lab wet treatment, MRT_{soil}, MRT_f and MRT_s, were
30 always lower in the oak savanna than in the ponderosa pine soils (Table 1, Figure 6).
31 There was 3 times more N per unit of C in savanna soils than in ponderosa soils (C/N
32 ratios in Table 1). It is well known that N limits enzyme production, microbial biomass
33 and ultimately SOM decomposition (Melillo et al. 1982, Henriksen and Breland 1999,
34 Alison 2005) which may partially explain the differences in palatability of SOM between
35 ecosystems. Though MRT_{soil} was expected to increase with time as the fast pool
36 disappears and SOM became more stable (Townsend et al 1997, Trumbore 2000, Holland
37 et al. 2000, Gaudinsky and Trumbore 2004), MRT_{soil} showed an unexpected late
38 decreased in the four soils (Figure 6). By the end of the incubation its value was close to
39 its initial one and distinct from the expected values of MRT_s for the slow C pool (Figure
40 6) indicating that old/recalcitrant OM might not necessarily be associated to longer mean
41 residence times.

42
43 The relatively high soil decomposition rates observed in the trenched pine plot (Figure
44 2a) emphasizes this idea. During 2003 soil respiration of the trenched soils accounted
45 roughly for half the respiration recorded at the control plots (Misson et al. 2006). In turn,
46 soil respiration in control soils was similar during both years. Because soil moisture

1 values during summer 2003 and 2006 were very similar (compare Figure 2 with Figure 1
2 in Misson et al 2006), the observed relative increase in metabolic activity of the trenched
3 respect control soils could not be explained by differences in soil moisture or by
4 incorporation of fine roots to the soil (Table 1). Lab incubations confirmed the field trend
5 observations (Figures 3a and 3b), and despite the lower C content of the trenched soils
6 (Table 1) SOM decomposition was slightly higher than under non-trenched soils (Figure
7 3a and 3b).

8
9 We therefore hypothesize that the existing microbial community may have acclimated to
10 changes in the quality of the SOM. Recent studies have pointed out that first order
11 kinetics models may not be a good predictor of ecosystem functioning because they do
12 not reflect changes in the behavior of the microbial community (Schimel 1995, Stark and
13 Firestone 1996, Schimel and Gulledge 1998, Balser et al. 2001, Balser and Firestone
14 2004, Hawkes et al. 2005). Characteristics of microbial ecophysiology, such as stress-
15 driven changes in rate of metabolic activity or changes in the composition of the active
16 microbial community, are not taken into account by these models. Quality and
17 availability of substrate (soluble short-chain molecules or complex molecules) favor
18 different ecological strategies (e.g. cheater vs extracellular enzyme producers, r-strategic
19 vs. K-strategic) (Fontaine and Barot 2005, Allison 2005). More labile carbon, that is
20 readily decomposable (e.g. at the beginning of the incubation or in the non-trenched
21 plots) would favor opportunistic/cheaters (r-strategic) over enzyme producers (K-
22 strategic). Depletion of the labile C may have favored organism able to produce
23 extracellular enzymes able to break down more stable fractions of SOM (Allison 2005). It
24 therefore might be that SOM decomposition not only depends on the substrate
25 biochemistry, but also on the ability of the existing microbial community to decompose
26 the available substrate. Moreover, since no living roots were present either in soil cores or
27 trenched soils, there was a lack of competition for nutrients, favoring SOM
28 decomposition.

29 30 *Water limitation and organic matter decomposition*

31
32 Though soil moisture limited seasonality of soil CO₂ efflux more in the oak savanna than
33 in the pine site (Figure 4), summer water levels increased substantially the MRT_{soil} of
34 both ecosystems (Figure 6). The strong increase of microbial decomposition (Figure 3)
35 and decrease in mean residence time experienced by oak soils when rewetted after
36 collection (see RITT in Table 3) further highlights the role that sporadic rain events plays
37 during the dry periods in these ecosystems (Xu et al. 2004, Misson et al. 2005), when
38 temperatures are also the highest (Figure 2). As indicated above, labile plant-derived
39 substrate is prevented for decomposition during the extremely dry summer, but rain
40 stimulation of microbial activity plays a very important role in the C balance of this
41 ecosystem during dry periods (Xu et al. 2004). Our results, therefore, highlight the
42 influence that the combination of water limitation, labile inputs to soil and sporadic
43 summer rain events may have in soil C dynamics of these two Mediterranean ecosystems.

44
45 Moisture limitation affected the temperature sensitivity of SOM decomposition
46 differently (Figure 4a and 4b, Figure 7). Under moderate summer drought, seasonal Q₁₀

1 decreased when drought-affected data (defined as in Xu and Qi 2001) were included
2 (dotted lines in Figures 4a and 4b). A gradual decrease of soil water content during spring
3 and summer (Figure 2c) affected both fine roots and microbial metabolic activity because
4 diffusion of nutrients and substrate occurs in water medium (Belnap et al. 2003).
5 Limitation to soil metabolic activity will therefore increase as soil water content
6 decreases during the season (e. g. Xu and Qi 2001, Reichstein et al. 2002, Curiel Yuste et
7 al. 2003, Xu et al. 2004). On short-time scales, temperature sensitivity of microbial
8 decomposition was always lower in dry than in wet soils (Figure 7). SOM decomposition
9 in the relatively dry pine soils showed typically a positive relationship with temperature
10 ($Q_{10}>1$; Figure 7a and 7b), but the relationship between temperature and SOM in the very
11 dry oak soils was typically negative ($Q_{10}<1$; 7c and 7d). Under field conditions we found
12 the same trend during dry periods (Figure 8), which supported the results obtained under
13 lab conditions. Low values of Q_{10} , were expected for dry soils because microbes live in
14 the water films where a large portion of their metabolism takes place (Harris 1981, Paul
15 and Clark 1996). Values of Q_{10} below 1 were nonetheless less expected. Because soil
16 water potential is a function of temperature and the relative humidity (Rh) of air in the
17 pore space, relatively fast changes in temperature performed in this experiment might
18 have affected soil water potential and soil metabolic activity:

$$\psi = R * T / M * (\ln Rh) \quad \text{equation 11}$$

22 Where ψ is soil water potential (MPa), R the Universal Gas Constant ($8.31 * 10^{-3}$ L Mpa
23 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), T the observed soil temperature at measurement time (K), M ($18.05 * 10^{-3}$ l
24 mol) is the molecular mass of water and Rh is the relative humidity. A reduction in soil
25 water potential is exacerbated by the fact that soil temperature increases more when soil
26 pore space gets drier, Figure 9 shows that as soils gets both warmer (high T) and drier
27 (low relative humidity) soil water potential can change from -6 to less than -12 MPa in
28 the vicinity of the existing drought-tolerant microbes.

30 *Temperature sensitivity of microbial decomposition*

32 The relatively low values of Q_{10} (Typically below the physiological value of 2) found
33 under lab conditions (Figure 7) were below those reported at ecosystem level,
34 independent of the temporal scale used (Raich & Schesinger 1992, Xu and Qi 2001,
35 Janssens and Pilegaard 2003) and in former studies of soil decomposition (Kirschbaum
36 1995, Katterer et al. 1998, Holland et al. 2000, Reichstein et al. 2000, Dalias 2001, Fierer
37 et al 2003 and 2005, Fang et al. 2005). Because temperature sensitivity of respiration
38 decreases as temperature increases (Lloyd and Taylor 1994, Atkins and Tjoelker 2003,
39 Janssens and Pilegaard 2003, Price and Sowers 2004), the relatively high temperatures
40 used in this study may partly explain the low Q_{10} values obtained. Values of Q_{10} expected
41 for the temperature range of the study derived from an Arrhenius-like equation (Lloyd
42 and Taylor 1994), using a constant E_a of 51 kJ mol^{-1} (the typical value for enzyme
43 kinetics performed in laboratory; Van't Hoff 1898) would be 1.94. This value resembles
44 those observed in the early stages of the incubation for the wet soils (Figure 7).

1 Depletion of the fast C pool influenced the temperature sensitivity of microbial
2 decomposition (Figure 10). This depletion influenced differently both ecosystems:
3 temperature sensitivity of decomposition expressed as Q_{10} increased in oak soils while C_f
4 was gradually depleted but decreased in pine control soils (Figure 10b, Table 4). Theory
5 states that temperature sensitivity of the organic matter should increase as the quality of
6 the substrate to be decomposed decreases (Bosatta and Agren 1998) which supports the
7 increase in Q_{10} found in oak savannah soils (Figure 10b). This theory has been supported
8 recently by experimental evidence (Fierer et al. 2003, Fierer et al. 2005). However, this
9 theory can't explain the observed decrease in Q_{10} in pine soils (Figure 10b) the consistent
10 decrease in temperature sensitivity observed in all four soils by the incubation end
11 (Figure 7) or the low values of seasonal temperature sensitivity obtained in the
12 older/more recalcitrant trenched soils (Figure 4a).

13
14 A number of observational 'deviations' from the kinetic theory recently reported (Liski et
15 al. 1999, Giardina and Ryan 2003, Fang et al. 2005) suggest that the complexity of the
16 process transcend the single theory (Davidson and Janssens 2006). Other factors such as
17 physical or biochemical accessibility to substrate by microbes (Davidson et al. 2006),
18 water availability and substrate diffusion (Davidson & Janssens 2006) or microbial
19 population dynamics (Monson et al. 2006) also affect the response to temperature of
20 SOM decomposition. Temperature sensitivity for most enzymatic kinetics correspond to
21 a Q_{10} around 2, which resembles the initial Q_{10} values of non trenched plots under no
22 water limitation in this study (Figure 7). The subsequent decrease in Q_{10} might be
23 explained by a decrease in access to substrate of the enzymatic machinery, independently
24 of a hypothetical increase in temperature sensitivity (Davidson et al. 2006). However, our
25 calculations suggest that decomposition rates of recalcitrant organic matter were not
26 necessarily lower in this study (see Figure 6). Possible shifts in microbial community
27 composition as suggested above from fast growing r-strategic to slow growing K-
28 strategic dominated community may have also included microbial biomass as a
29 confounding factor in our Q_{10} calculations. Therefore though decomposition of more
30 recalcitrant organic matter may be more dependent on temperature, other mechanisms
31 such as SOM stabilization or decreases in growth rates of the microbial community may
32 counteract this effect.

33 34 *Conceptual Model of decomposition*

35
36 Based on our observations, the scheme in Figure 11 offers a guideline for modeling both
37 microbial decomposition rates and temperature sensitivity of the process. We defined six
38 factors as potential sources of variability on SOM decomposition: 1. Labile C inputs from
39 active root plants (GPP); 2. Quality of SOM associated to the intrinsic biochemical
40 properties of vegetation (q); 3. Degree of physical, chemical and/or biochemical
41 protection of the substrate ($[S]$); 4. Rate of microbial respiration (μ); 5. Soil moisture (θ)
42 and 6. Soil temperature (T).

43
44 The subjectivity of SOM decomposition to most of these factors has been described in
45 semi-mechanistically models such as CENTURY (e.g. Parton et al. 1987). However there

1 exists lot of uncertainties regarding the mechanisms of photosynthetic control of SOM
2 decomposition and its role in temporal and spatial variation of heterotrophic activity.

3
4 Aggregation formation (physical protection), adsorption onto mineral surfaces (chemical
5 protection) or biochemical transformation of SOM towards more complex substrates
6 (biochemical protection) are the three mechanisms responsible of SOM protection ($\Delta[S]$)
7 (Sollins et al. 1996, Thornley et al. 2001, Six et al. 2002). Though some evidence
8 suggests saturation levels in SOM stabilization (Six et al. 2002) it is not clear at which
9 extent increasing temperatures may increase the degree of physical and physico-chemical
10 stabilization of SOM (Thornley et al. 2001).

11
12 Changes in microbial respiration caused by changes in the intrinsic respiration of the
13 existing microbes (low efficiency) or changes in the microbial community composition
14 (adaptation and higher efficiency) may affect the mean residence time of SOM and its
15 response to temperature. Questions to be answered are the time scale and time line of
16 microbial community adaptation to climatic changes and how it will affect MRT_{soil}

17
18 The net temperature sensitivity can be altered by a number of factors too (see right part of
19 scheme). Those factors can obscure the intrinsic and direct temperature sensitivity of the
20 process ($Q_{10} \approx 2$). Three different scenarios were defined in the scheme. Dashed arrows
21 connecting the three arbitrary scenarios indicate the possibility of transition among
22 scenarios in case there are deviations from the conditions in which one scenario was
23 defined, e.g. an increase in photosynthetic activity during spring may probably increase
24 root exudation (ΔGPP), causing a transition from scenario 2 to 1.

25
26 Scenario number 1 represents soils under no water limitation, high plant activity and
27 exudates production, or high exposure to labile C, such as snow melting ($+\Delta GPP$). Under
28 these conditions it is likely that values of Q_{10} will approach the physiological value of 2.
29 Changes in fine root activity (ΔGPP) via exudates production and SOM decomposition
30 priming will be a confounding factor on calculations of Q_{10} at seasonal time scales. On
31 shorter time scales successional changes in microbial community structure from r- to K-
32 strategic dominated communities ($\Delta\mu$) may also act as a confounding factor. Since these
33 microbial populations exhibit different growth rates (Fontaine and Barot 2005) elevated
34 Q_{10} 's may respond to fast increases in the biomass respiring (r-strategy) when root
35 exudation increases.

36
37 Scenario 2 represents soils receiving little or no labile C ($-\Delta GPP$), therefore less quality
38 of SOM ($-\Delta q$). Under conditions with no water limitation, the kinetic theory predicts an
39 increase in the temperature dependency of substrate oxidation. We suggest that other
40 factors, specially the accessibility to substrate ($\Delta[S]$) by microbes, may counteract the
41 increase in energy dependence of decomposition of recalcitrant substrates (Davidson et
42 al. 2006).

43
44 Scenario 3, represent water limited the soils ($\Delta\theta$) subjected to temperature and water
45 fluctuations (summer drying/rewetting or spring snow melts). In this scenario sporadic
46 rain events will eventually bring the flux to pre-drought values, and temperature

1 sensitivity to Q_{10} values close to two. The magnitude of the increase will depend
2 primarily on the amount of labile C stored in soils after drought-induced microbial
3 mortality and secondarily on the quality of SOM. Successional changes on microbial
4 community ($\Delta\mu$) may act as confounding factor too. The observed negative relationship
5 between decomposition and temperature in the driest soils could not be explained and
6 future experiments should be designed to understand this effect.

7
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9
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16

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1 **Table 1.** Biochemical and physical properties of the four soil, ponderosa pine trenched
2 (bt), ponderosa pine control (bc), oak savanna open area (to) and oak savanna
3 understorey (tu). % of N and C represents the percentage of Nitrogen and Carbon
4 respectively. C and N represent the quantities of the same elements. ‘Moisture dry’ and
5 ‘ ψ dry’ represents respectively the soil water content and soil water potential of soil
6 under field conditions. ‘Moisture wet’ was the soil water content after soils were rewetted
7 (wet treatment). Turnover C_1 and C_2 represent respectively the MRTs of fast (C_1) and
8 slow (C_2) C pools of the soils calculated with equation 7 (C/k).
9

	bt	bc	to	tu
roots (kg m^{-2})	0	1.3(1.5)	1.5(1.0)	1.4(2.4)
litter (kg m^{-2})	3.0(29)	2.8(24)	.6(3)	1.4(23)
% N	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.3
% C	6.4	13.9	1.7	3.9
Soil N_{total} (kg m^{-2})	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2
Soil C_{total} (kg m^{-2})	2.9	5.1	1.4	2.6
C/N ratio	28.5	29.6	10.7	12.5
moisture dry (g/g)	10	14.5	2.4	4.2
ψ dry (MPa)	-1.5	-0.25	-15	-10
moisture wet (g/g)	24.3	28.9	18.9	22.1
MRT_f (d)	-	18.0	12.0	12.0
MRT_s (y)	4.6	6.8	2.0	2.1
Total C respired (Kg C m^{-2})	0.2	0.2	0.22	0.43
% of C respired	7	4	16	16

1 **Table 2.** Calculated values and statistics (t tail and p-value) of the coefficients (C_1 , k_1 and
 2 k_2) obtained when flux data expressed as F_a was fitted to *Equations 7, 8 and 9*. Adjusted
 3 correlation coefficient (Adj R^2) and p value (P) of the regression are also reported.
 4 Asterisk (*) following values represent coefficients significantly different from 0 for a
 5 95% confident interval. The treatments are ponderosa pine trenched (bt), ponderosa pine
 6 control (bc), oak savanna open area (to) and oak savanna understorey (tu).
 7

treatments	Model	C_f (g m ⁻²)	K_f (d ⁻¹)	K_s (d ⁻¹)	Adj R^2	P-value
bt	1	0	0	6.00E-04*	0.99	<0.0001
	2	1.4(0.2)*	0.04(6e-3) *	3.00e-03*	0.99	<0.0001
	3	2.1(6.5)	0.3(1.4)	8.00E-04*	0.85	<0.0001
bc	1	17.8(0.9)*	0.06(0.01)*	4.0E-04*	0.99	<0.0001
	2	22.6 (3) *	0.05 (0.01) *	4.00E-03*	0.99	<0.0001
	3	9.2 (4.2) *	0.15 (0.09) *	4.00E-04	0.91	<0.0001
to	1	32.2(3.4)*	0.08(0.01)*	1.4E-03*	0.99	<0.0001
	2	42.2 (5.7)	0.06(0.01) *	3.00E-03*	0.99	<0.0001
	3	20(3) *	0.16(0.03) *	0.1*	0.97	<0.0001
tu	1	61.4(6.8)*	0.08(0.01)*	1.3E-03*	0.99	<0.0001
	2	78 (10) *	0.06(0.01) *	0.05*	0.99	<0.0001
	3	51.2(8) *	0.1(0.02) *	1.20E-03*	0.98	<0.0001

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1 **Table 3.** Mean residence time of SOM at time 0 (MRT_0) calculated with *equation 12* for
 2 the dry and the wet treatment, and the relative increase in MRT_0 when reweted (wet
 3 treatment) for the four studied soils. Statistics of the fit are also given: standard error of
 4 the mean (SEM), correlation coefficient (R^2) and p-value. The treatments are ponderosa
 5 pine trenched (bt), ponderosa pine control (bc), oak savanna open area (to) and oak
 6 savanna understorey (tu).

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treatment	wet				dry				RIMRT
	MRT_0	SEM	R^2	P-value	MRT_0	SEM	R^2	P-value	
bt	3.0	0.6	0.5	0.2	4.5	1.0	0.5	0.3	1.5
bc	3.8	0.3	0.8	0.0	11.1	1.4	0.6	0.2	2.9
to	1.0	0.1	0.8	0.0	3.9	1.2	0.7	0.2	3.9
tu	0.9	0.2	0.8	0.0	4.3	0.5	1.0	0.0	4.5

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1 **Table 4.** Slopes of the linear fit of Q_{10} vs time for the wet treatment (Figure 8). Statistics
 2 of the fit are also given: standard error of the mean (SEM), correlation coefficient (R^2)
 3 and p-value. The treatments are ponderosa pine trenched (bt), ponderosa pine control
 4 (bc), oak savanna open area (to) and oak savanna understorey (tu).

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	slope	SEM	R^2	P-value
bt	-0.00251	0.00164	0.37	0.2017
bc	-0.00307	0.00185	0.35	0.15815
to	-0.00441	0.00177	0.55	0.05514
tu	-0.00513	0.00111	0.81	0.00565

8

1 **Figure captions**

2
3 **Figure 1.** Increase in CO₂ concentrations within the analysis chamber of the IRGA
4 during a measurement period (around 40 seconds). Interval within the two vertical bars
5 represents the measurement interval used to calculate the flux.

6 **Figure 2.** 2005 Seasonal evolution of soil respiration ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; left panels), soil
7 temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$; middle panels) and soil volumetric water content (% vol; right panels)
8 for the four studied soils. Data from the ponderosa pine soils (trenched and control) are
9 represented in the above panels, while oak savanna soils (understorey and open) are
10 represented in the panels below. Vertical bars in soil respiration panels represent the
11 standard error of the mean.

12 **Figure 3.** Temporal evolution of decomposition-derived soil CO₂ fluxes in the wet
13 (closed circles) and dry (open circles) treatments in the four studied soils: ponderosa pine
14 trenched (a), ponderosa pine control (b) oak savanna open (c) and oak savanna
15 understorey (d). Error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

16 **Figure 4.** Field estimates of soil respiration as a function of soil temperature (5 cm depth
17 soil) under no water limitations in a) ponderosa pine trench and b) ponderosa pine
18 control. Solid lines represent the Q₁₀ fit of the field data under no water limitations (solid
19 triangles), dotted lines the same but including data obtained under water limitations (open
20 triangles) and dashed lines the initial Q₁₀ fit obtained in soil incubations for the same
21 soils. Field estimates of soil respiration as a function of soil moisture at 15 cm depth in c)
22 open areas and d) understorey areas of the oak savanna ecosystem. Solid lines represent
23 the fit of field data (solid triangles) to the Boltzman sigmoid function (*equation 6*).
24 Dotted lines represent the fit to the SOM decomposition data obtained in the lab (open
25 circles). Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. Values of temperature
26 sensitivity (Q₁₀), correlation coefficient (R²) and p values are also given.

27 **Figure 5.** a) Contribution of C_f decomposition to total decomposition-derived CO₂ efflux
28 at time 0, calculated with *equations 10 and 11*; b) Decomposition-derived CO₂ effluxes at
29 time 0 and 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ vs initial C_f quantity calculated with *equation 7*.

30 **Figure 6.** Temporal evolution of SOM mean residence time (MRT_{soil}) in the wet (open
31 circles) and dry (closed triangles) treatments in the four studied soils: ponderosa pine
32 trenched (a), ponderosa pine control (b), oak savanna open (c) and oak savanna
33 understorey (d). Solid line represents the non-linear regression fit of the temporal
34 evolution of MRT_{soil} in the wet samples. Horizontal dotted lines represent the mean
35 residence time of the slow pool calculated by *equation 7*.

36 **Figure 7.** Temporal evolution of the sensitive to temperature of microbial decomposition
37 (expressed as Q₁₀) in the wet (open circles) and dry (closed triangles) treatments in the
38 four studied soils: ponderosa pine trenched (a), ponderosa pine control (b) oak savanna
39 open (c) and oak savanna understorey (d). Error bars represent the standard error of the
40 mean. Statistics of the linear fit are given in Table 4.

41 **Figure 8.** Diurnal variations in soil respiration measured in the field during dry events as
42 a function of soil temperature in: ponderosa pine trenched (a), ponderosa pine control (b)
43 oak savanna open (c) and oak savanna understorey (d). Error bars represent the standard
44 deviation

45 **Figure 9.** Modeled fluctuations of soil water potential as a function of soil temperature
46 for three different relative humidity's. Soil water potential was inferred from our soil

1 moisture values and existing water retention curves for these soils (data not shown).
2 Assuming a temperature of 25 °C and using *equation 11*, Rh was estimated as 0.93 for the
3 oak savanna soils.

4 **Figure 10.** a) Simulated depletion of C_f based on the initial C_f values (gC m^{-2}) and the
5 constant rate k_f (d^{-1}) for the three soils with initial values of C_f (see Table 2); b) Q_{10}
6 against the Log transformed inverse of the remaining C_f at each incubation measurement
7 date. Lines represent the linear fit for ponderosa pine control soils (solid line) and oak
8 savannah soils (dotted line).

9 **Figure 11.** Schematic representation of the influence exerted by several environmental
10 factors on the rate of SOM decomposition and its temperature sensitivity. On the left axis
11 we represent factors involved in the magnitude of the decomposition-derived flux and on
12 the right side we depict factors involved in the temperature sensitivity of the
13 decomposition-derived flux. The upper half of the scheme accounts for factors affecting
14 SOM decomposition under no water limitation (non-water limited) and the lower portion
15 depicts effects of water limitation (water limited). Except for temperature, the influence
16 of each environmental factor is assessed in the vertical axis, specifying the sign of the
17 influence as negative (-) positive (+) or no influence (=) over decomposition rates and
18 temperature sensitivity. Question marks are added to those factors whose influence needs
19 further study. Solid lines represent the changes in decomposition rate as a function of
20 temperature that correspond to a Q_{10} of 2. Dotted lines represent deviations from the
21 expected Q_{10} relationship of 2 (typical sensitivity of most enzymatic processes).

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1 **Figure 1**

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1 **Figure 2**

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1 **Figure 10**

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1 Figure 11

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